

A Network Analysis on Greater Cairo, using Person Trip Survey Data

Hiroshi KATO^{1*}, Eri DEGAWA², Susumu SATO³, Yutaka GOTO⁴

¹Hitotsubashi University, ²Chiba University, ³Tokyo University of Foreign Studies (ILCAA), ⁴Yokohama City University

Abstract: A person trip survey was carried out by the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) in Cairo in 2001. It was a big data that sampled about 117,000 individuals. The person trip survey is, as also called the 'traffic fact finding survey', an investigation with practical purposes such as traffic plans and city master plan development. In addition, the person trip survey data have been used in social science studies such as consumer models and influenza infection course simulations that focus on 'person flow.', since they include the detailed information about the individual attributes and their daily life patterns. This paper is an attempt to use the person trip survey data mentioned above for historical study on Greater Cairo, taking up the people who move by animals (the animal drawn) as a case study, by linking the following three kinds of data and information by GIS: 1) Statistical data of population censuses by the district (qism) administrative unit, 2) Geographic information, including historical and contemporary maps, satellite imagery, and administrative digital maps, and 3) Person trip survey data,

Keywords: Area Studies, Greater Cairo, Person trip survey, Network analysis by GIS

1. Purpose of the presentation

This paper is a theoretical attempt to analyze the dynamic formation process of Great Cairo, focusing on the movement of people who are living across the boundaries of the administrative units.

The data and information on which this paper is based are the three kinds of source materials: 1) Statistical data of population censuses by the district administrative unit since 1897, 2) Geographic information: historical and contemporary maps, digital administrative maps and satellite imageries, and 3) Person trip survey data in Cairo in 2001. The point of this paper is not to show concrete research results, but to introduce new research method ideas for the area study on Greater Cairo, using three different kinds of source materials.

What is Greater Cairo?

Greater Cairo is not a municipality or governorate, but a living area that included neighboring governorates around Cairo governorate, which is now a mega location with a population of 20 million. In other words, Greater Cairo is not a formal administrative unit, but rather an informal residential area, whose border has been undefined and has shifted historically depending on demographic and socio-economic circumstances⁽¹⁾.

Administrative system in Egypt

Today, the largest administrative unit in Egypt is the governorate (*muhāfaẓa*). The governorate is subdivided into urban district (*qism*) and rural county (*markaz*). The smallest administrative units are the urban town (*shiyākha*) and rural village (*qarya*). Here, *qism* is used as the analytical unit for the expansion of Greater Cairo from the administrative point of view (Map 1). In fact, the expansion of Cairo's residential area has been reflected in the vicissitude of *qisms* since 1897, the year of the real first population census.

Figure 1 - Qisms in Greater Cairo in 2006.

2. Data and information

Population Census

The most important data for the area study on Greater Cairo have been published by the Central Agency for Public Mobilization and Statistics (CAPMAS). Indeed, most studies on Greater Cairo have used CAPMAS macro aggregated data, especially its population census data. In Egypt, the first population census was conducted in 1882. However, this was a preparatory one, and the first true population census was conducted in 1897. Thereafter, a census was executed at nearly 10-year intervals.

The population census data are useful for the study on Greater Cairo because of the following four reasons. First, they are the most accessible data officially published by CAPMAS. Second, they are time-series data since 1897, although some of their formats vary. Third, they include both basic demographics and other socio-economics such as occupational statistics. Fourth, they include statistics for the small Egyptian administrative units.

The macro aggregated data by *qism* show general demographic and socio-economic trends and patterns, by administrative unit, for the Greater Cairo people. However, they are rarely used in connection with the institutional transition of administrative units. One reason for this is the repeated shifts in administrative units due to the rapid expansion of Cairo's residential

* Corresponding Author
Hitotsubashi University, kato@econ.hit-u.ac.jp

area since the middle of the 20th century. Table 1 is the database on the population in *qisms* in Greater Cairo, 1897-2019, and shows the change of the number of *qisms* since 1897, being based on the census data. The gray zone made up Greater Cairo⁽²⁾.

No.	Documentation	1897	1907	1917	1927	1937	1947	1950	1955	1970	1984	1994	2008	2019
1	Cairo													
2	Cairo													
3	Cairo													
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30	Qibria													
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36	Qibria													
37	Cairo													
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Note (1) The light gray units are classified as *markaz* (nos. 32, 58, 61, and 69) or suburban cities (nos. 33–36), though they were considered to constitute Greater Cairo in 2019. (2) Duqqi (no. 54) belonged to Cairo governorate from 1917 to 1960. (3) Giza (no. 65), part of which belonged to Cairo in 1937. (4) Part of Imbaba (no. 55) was a *qism* in 1966, while its other part has been a *markaz* that means a rural district until the present.

Table 1 - Database on the population in *qisms* in Greater Cairo, 1897-2019.

Geographic information

The first mapping of modern Egypt was the remarkable, so-called, Napoleon’s maps produced at the beginning of the 19th century by French scholars during Napoleon’s 1798 expedition to Egypt (Map 2 and 3). After that, the most important modern mapping contribution used scientific ordnance survey techniques, which began as part of the agricultural land survey project from 1892 to 1907⁽³⁾. Complete mapping of Egypt was finished by the 1930s. Based on these published maps, the maps that contained specific information, such as irrigation and transportation were produced.

Figure 2 - Napoleon’s map around Cairo (1818).
Figure 3 - Cairo drawn by French during the French occupation.

Source of Map2: David Rumsey Map Collection.

Source of Map3: Municipality of Cairo, *Master Plan of Cairo*, Ministry of Municipal & Rural Affairs, Municipality of Cairo, Planning Commission, S.O.P.-Press, 1957.

In addition to these historical and contemporary maps, the digital administrative maps and many types of satellite imagery (Map 4) are available. Especially valuable are the digital administrative maps that use the smallest villages and towns as units, which CAPMAS created for the population census survey (Map 1). These maps are useful in our research to produce many kinds of digital maps, by data coding of population census data and overlaying it on the maps of three kind.

Figure 4 - Satellite imagery around Greater Cairo

Person trip survey data

A person trip survey was carried out by the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) in Cairo in 2001 to collect basic data on the transportation network of the Greater Cairo area. After the person trip survey, JICA undertook a global survey of Greater Cairo’s urban development and maintenance plans during 2007–2008⁽⁴⁾. Before the 2001 survey, Cairo person trip surveys were also conducted by JICA in 1966 and 1989⁽⁵⁾. But unfortunately, these data are not available.

The 2001 Cairo person trip survey is a big data that sampled about 117,000 individuals and 570,000 trips. And it contains a wealth of information on the everyday life of people in Greater Cairo such as age (8 categories), traffic means (23 types), occupation (19 types) and purpose of movement (13 types)⁽⁶⁾. So, the 2001 Cairo person trip survey data represent valuable source material on the daily patterns of Greater Cairo’s inhabitants at the beginning of the 21st century, from a novel flow-of-the-person viewpoint, as will be explained⁽⁷⁾.

3. Analysis by combining statistical data and geographic information

Map 5 is a superimposed map of *qisms* for five census years from 1897 to 1986 (1897, 1927, 1947, 1960, 1986) based on the data in Table 1 shows the expansion of Greater Cairo as an increase in *qisms*.

Figure 5 - Expansion of Greater Cairo viewed from the transition of *qisms*.

Map 6 and Map 7 are the maps in which Map 1 is overlaid on the historical maps in 1945 and 1985. The white line is the boundary of *qism*. The light blue space in Map 6 and the light pink space in Map 7 are the ranges of Greater Cairo as the aggregations of *qism* in 1947 and 1986 respectively.

Figure 6 - Boundary of *qism* and the range of Greater Cairo in 1947.

Figure 7 - Boundary of *qism* and the range of Greater Cairo in 1986.

4. Analysis by combining the person trip survey data and the geographic information: Case study of the animal drawn.

Macro aggregated population data by administrative unit, linked with geographic information, show general trends and patterns across a range of activities among Greater Cairo’s inhabitants. However, this analysis does not provide information about the actual areas in which the people of Greater Cairo lived their lives.

In contrast, the person trip survey data reveal where people actually lived out their lives, which was not restricted to administrative units. The person trip survey is an investigation with practical purposes such as traffic plans and city master plan development. However, they have also been used in social science studies such as consumer models, influenza infection course simulations

that focus on ‘person flow.’, because the person trip survey produces big data, including detailed information about the individual attributes of large samples and their daily life patterns as explained above.

Then, we will take up the animal drawn (the people who move by animals) as a case study. The total animal drawn sample was 114 individuals, who took 221 trips. Thus, the animal drawn is a minor subset of the survey and thus qualitatively and quantitatively exceptional. The reason why such a minor social category as the animal drawn is taken up is that they are a social category with simple attributes, which can easily be interpreted with few indices, so they are more appropriate as an analysis target than other social categories with complex attributes whose explanation would have required significant information⁽⁸⁾.

Map 8 is a map on which the trips of the movement of the animal drawn on the administrative digital map of *qisms* and the satellite imagery around Greater Cairo. The white line is the boundary of *qism*. An arrow (→) shows the start point and arrival point of the movement of the animal drawn. Apparently, the living area of the animal drawn is the rural areas on the outskirts of Greater Cairo, moving across its boundaries. In fact, most of them are farmers, as shown in Map 9 and Map 10. Previously, the movements by animals were seen frequently in the city of Cairo, but today, they are seen only in the suburbs of Greater Cairo, due to the building of roads and subways.

Note White line is the boundary of *qism*, and red line is the route of the movement by the animal drawn today.

Figure 8 - Scope of the animal drawn movement.

Figure 9 - Ratio of the animal drawn trip by *qism*

Figure 10 - Ratio of farmers trip by *qism*

This is so-called “the approach from a ‘person –flow’ perspective”. The advantage of this approach is shown simply by the fact that the behaviors among those surveyed can be visualized by their dispersion on map points, not by aggregation within administrative units. And the person trip data show not only the scope, but also the intention of people’s movements (To work, To school/institution, To home, Shopping or Eating, Other, and Meeting or other business purpose) and the daily schedule (from 3 to 22 o'clock), as shown in Map 11. So, the person trip data combined with the geographic information could provide a glimpse into the real lives of the people of Greater Cairo, from the viewpoint of person flow, while the macro aggregated statistical data reflect the conditions or context of behaviors among those surveyed.

Figure 11 - Purpose and time of the animal drawn movement

5. Concluding remarks

It is apparent that person trip data may open up new directions for the area study of Greater Cairo's region from a 'person-flow' perspective, when connected with auxiliary source materials of population census data by administrative units, and geographical information such as historical maps and satellite imageries. In this paper, the effectiveness of this approach for the area study on Greater Cairo was shown using a case study of the animal drawn.

The effectiveness of this approach will be clarified when the subjects of analysis are expanded to social categories with large samples and diverse attributes. It is certain that the volume of data processing will be enormous. But, much of this can be aided by technological progress and the development of analysis tools. Lastly, I wish to say again that the purpose of this paper is to introduce a new research approach, and then, detailed analysis of the data is expected in the future.

Acknowledgments

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Note

- (1) There is a lot of literature on Cairo. Among them, the following should be taken up as a classical study. Janet Abu-Lughod, *Cairo: 1001 Years of the City Victorious*. Princeton University Press, 1971.
- (2) For details. see H. KATO, E. DEGAWA, S. SATO and Y. GOTO "Historical Transitions of the *Qisms* (Districts) of Greater Cairo", *Mediterranean World* 25, Hitotsubashi University, 2021.
- (3) H. G. Lyons, *The Cadastral Survey of Egypt, 1892–1907*, Cairo, 1908.

(4) JICA undertook a global survey of the urban development and maintenance plan of Greater Cairo in 2007–2008. This was titled "The survey on the sustainable urban development and maintenance plan of Greater Cairo" (final report in 2008: https://openjicareport.jica.go.jp/618/618/618_405_11893401.html).

(5) Akita Nakamura et al. "The Introduction on the database of the urban traffic development surveys by JICA: Person trip data on 11 cities in the world", (Japanese) *Journal of the Japan Society of Traffic Engineers*, Special issue, 2004 (<http://www2.kaiyodai.ac.jp/~hyodo/JICA-PT.pdf>).

(6) Following is the items or categories in the 2001 Cairo person trip survey. 1) Age (8 categories): 7–9 years, 10–19 years, 20–29 years, 30–39 years, 40–49 years, 50–60 years, more than 60 years, and unknown. 2) Traffic means (23 types): on foot, bicycle, motorcycle, private car driver, private car passenger, pickup for passengers, taxi, shared taxi, public minibus, public bus, public A/C bus, cooperative minibus, company (work) car, factory/company bus, school bus, truck for passengers, Nile bus, tram, Heliopolis metro, underground metro, ENR train, animal -drawn vehicle, other, stay, and unknown. 3) Occupation (19 types): legislature; administrative management worker; professional worker; technician or assistant; clerk or related worker; sales or service worker; farmer, fisher, or hunter; craftsmen or related worker; production worker; unskilled worker; other; student (primary, secondary, high school, technical or university), housewife, retired, jobless, and working person or no answer. 4) Purpose of movement (13 types): to work, to school/institution, to home, selling or delivering, meeting or other business purpose, return to workplace, shopping or eating, sending or fetching, recreation, medical treatment, social visit or other private purpose, other, and no answer.

(7) For details. See Y. GOTO, S. SATO and H. KATO "Person Trip Survey Data as a Source Material for the Study of the Greater Cairo Residential Area. A Case Study on Animal Drawn Transportation at the Beginning of the 21st Century", *Mediterranean World* 25, Hitotsubashi University, 2021.

(8) Following is the attributes of animal drawn and their numbers. 1) Age (6 categories): 10–19 years (13 samples), 20–29 years (23 samples), 30–39 years (25 samples), 40–49 years (26 samples), 50–60 years (17 samples), more than 60 years (9 samples), and unknown (1 samples), 2) Occupation (9 types): farmer, fisher, or hunter (84 samples), sales or service worker (14 samples), unskilled worker (5 samples), legislature; administrative management worker (3 samples), craftsmen or related worker (3 samples), primary student (2 samples), housewife (1 samples), production workers and workers related (1 samples), and others (1 samples).. 3) Purpose of movement (6 types): to work (102 trips), meeting or other business purpose (8 trips), to school/institution (1 trips), shopping or eating (1 trips), other (2 trips), and to home (107 trips).